

Non-operative management of anal fissure: success vs failure

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Abstract: Anal fissure is a linear rip or ulcer in the anal mucosa. Defecation causes a searing agony, "like passing shattered glass," according to patients, followed by hours of scorching sensation in the anus. The most common presenting symptoms are distress during and after defecation. Women of childbearing age and beyond, as well as those who have just given birth, are the most likely to experience fissures. Anal fissure occurs in around 11% of people during the course of their lives. In this article, we analyze the available data to determine if non-surgical therapies for anal fissure are effective and safe. Due to the danger of incontinence and the handicap that comes along with anal fissure surgery, non-invasive medical solutions have been researched. Recently, pharmaceutical approaches have been employed to obtain fissure healing by relaxing the anal smooth muscle, thereby accomplishing reversibly what occurs during surgery.

Keywords: anal fissure, fissure surgery, anal mucosa,

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Introduction

An anal fissure is an ulcer that develops in the squamous epithelium of the anus. It can be seen slightly distal to the mucocutaneous junction and is often found in the posterior midline [1]. In most cases, it causes discomfort both during the act of defecating and for up to two hours thereafter [2]. Atypical fissures may be many, located off the midline, big, irregular, or any combination of these characteristics. Inflammatory bowel illness, local or systemic cancer, venereal infection, trauma, TB, or chemotherapy are some of the possible causes of these symptoms.

There is a lack of consensus about the procedures that should be used to avoid fissures, and it is also unclear what causes the usual or benign fissure. It is the hypertonia of the internal anal sphincter that is the most common finding in typical fissures [3]. This hypertonia is so extreme that the discomfort that is induced by a fissure is assumed to be caused by ischemia. The alleviation of the spasm has been linked to the reduction of the related discomfort as well as the full and permanent healing of the fissure. Surgical treatment has traditionally been the method that has been utilized most frequently for easing the spasm. Anal stretch, open lateral sphincterotomy, closed lateral sphincterotomy, posterior midline sphincterotomy, and, to a lesser degree, dermal flap covering of the fissure are some of the surgical procedures that are routinely utilized for fissure in ano [3] [4]. Morbidity from these surgeries, which is mostly incontinence, was long considered to be exceedingly rare, but has been shown to be considerable in some recent publications. As a result,

there has been an uptick in interest in treatments that do not include the division of sphincter muscles. Within the scope of this review, non-operative methods will be discussed and evaluated.

Objectives

The goal of this study is to evaluate the efficacy and morbidity of various medical treatments for anal fissure.

Research Methodology

Type of study

The primary emphasis of this analysis is on research in which patients with anal fissures were assigned at random to receive nonsurgical treatment.

Types of participants

Patients of adult age who have an anal fissure are the primary focus of this analysis. The data in the papers encompass both adult and pediatric patients with acute and chronic fissures [1]. No randomized controlled trial (RCT) examined patients with atypical fissures (multiple, irregular, off the midline, or unrelated to hypertonia of the anal sphincter; seen often in IBD and malignancy). The term "chronic fissure" can be defined in both anatomical and temporal terms. If you've had pain for more than four weeks, or if you've had discomfort of shorter length on many occasions that were otherwise comparable, you probably have chronic pain. Chronicity can be seen in the form of a sentinel pile at the fissure's distal margin, piled-up fissure margins, exposed sphincter fibers at the fissure's base, or an inflammatory polyp at the fissure's inner boundary.

Chronicity can be defined by the presence of even one persistent indication or symptom. While prolonged hypertonia of the anal sphincter, hypertrophy, and ischemia may all play a role in the persistence of fissure in adults, it is unclear if these factors also contribute to the development of fissure in children [6]. As a result, treating children with anal fissure often involves non-invasive measures like laxatives and lubricants rather than invasive procedures like surgery. As a result of the failure of these drugs, researchers have begun exploring other treatments for youngsters. Adults with acute anal fissure may avoid developing chronic fissure if they receive prompt medical attention; this kind of fissure is believed to be more similar to pediatric anal fissure in its pathologic anatomy and to be curable in certain cases [7]. In reality, there isn't a ton of evidence supporting the procedures used to distinguish between acute and chronic anal fissure, so making that distinction can be difficult. How thoroughly a patient is questioned about previous bouts of anal discomfort may be crucial. There were reports that just dealt with acute fissures, and others that covered both acute and chronic cases.

Outcome measures

Persistence of the fissure (which is used synonymously with persistence of anal discomfort, the measure of effectiveness) and post-treatment mild incontinence were the two most often cited outcomes of therapy (the most commonly reported morbidity of operations for anal fissure; used synonymously with incontinence to flatus or anal seepage). Persistence and recurrence have been split out by several authors. Since anal fissures occur so often in nature, telling them apart can be tricky. Despite morphologic repair occurring between "attacks," anal fissures often worsen and then mend over time [8]. Accordingly, a "recurrence" or "persistence" may be defined as the return of pain and the anatomic discovery of a fissure after a time of healing and amelioration of symptoms following therapy. The distinction appears meaningless, given both outcomes represent therapy ineffectiveness.

Incontinence with both liquid and solid feces was also evaluated as a sign of more severe problems with defecation. In addition to headache with nitroglycerin, allergy or anaphylaxis in patients receiving repeated botulinum toxin injection, discomfort or infection at the injection site, and so on were analyzed as side effects unique to the medical therapy. There has been no recorded death or bleeding from this illness, however information on these outcomes was requested.

Pain reduction and anorectal manometric assessment of sphincter resting and squeeze pressure are two additional goals that are routinely reported [9]. Since various scales, instruments, and observational standards were utilized in the

many research that utilised either of these goals, comparing their results across studies is challenging. Healing of the anal fissure will be used as the primary outcome measure in the meta-analysis since it is the most objective and standardizable metric of effectiveness. Due to the cyclical nature of fissure, the time of the observation is a challenge. It was uncommon for all research participants to be followed for more than a year, but the best studies had follow-up durations that lengthy.

Data collection and analysis

Published reports and abstracts from meetings were combed through to compile this data, which was used to evaluate randomization, blinding, "intention to treat," and dropout rates, treatments, supporting measures (applied to both groups), dose, frequency, and crossovers. Nonhealing of the fissure (consisting of both recurrence and persistence) and Adverse events were used as dichotomous outcome indicators (including incontinence, headache, infection, anaphylaxis). Measuring how much pain was relieved and using anorectal manometry were also continuous outcome measures.

Results

This research comprised a total of 60 participants with a clinical diagnosis of chronic anal fissure. The participants in Group A ranged in age from 20 years old to 58 years old (mean age: 38.20 12.3 years). In Group B, the participants' ages ranged from 21 to 58 (mean: 38.4 13.03 years), with a minimum age of 21 and a maximum age of 58. There were 38 participants overall, of whom 38 (63.3%) were male and 22 (36.6%) female (11 in each group) (19 in each group).

Hundred percent of the 60 patients reported experiencing discomfort. The level of agony, however, varied. A total of 13 patients reported moderate pain (21.7%), while 47 patients (78.3%) reported severe pain. 43 (71.7%) of the cases had constipation, while 31 (51.7%) of the patients had rectal bleeding.

In terms of the location of the fissure, 11 patients (18.4%) had an anterior anal fissure, compared to 49 patients (81.6%) who had a posterior anal fissure. Women made up the majority of patients with anterior anal fissure. Clinical examination of the anal region revealed soreness in all 60 (100%) of the patients.

One patient reported chronic discomfort after lateral internal sphincterotomy, whereas 17 patients reported no pain following topical 0.2% nitroglycerin treatment.

After the end of the therapy, two weeks later, the bleeding was considered. At the 2-week follow-up, 17 patients in Group A—patients who received 0.2% nitroglycerin—presented with bleeding. Only two (6%) of the patients in Group B, which comprised patients who had lateral anal sphincterotomy, had bleeding at the 2-week mark.

10 individuals in Group A (33%) did not report any headaches while receiving topical 0.2% nitroglycerin therapy. Both Group A and Group B patients reported no incontinence; however, two (6.6%) patients had incontinence as a result of flatus and feces as a procedure-related consequence.

	Lateral sphincterotomy(n=30)	nitroglycerine(n=30)
No pain after treatment	17	28
No bleeding after treatment	17	29
No headache with treatment	10	30
No incontinence after the treatment	30	28
Fissures healed after 6 weeks	15	28

All of the patients recovered with nitroglycerin alone. Nitroglycerine based ointment being only available with prescription, many patients have reported to be successful fissure ointment in treating anal fissures. The danger of utilizing such medicines is low since most people who use nitroglycerin ointment only have headache while doing so, with no evident long-term negative effects. Therefore, medical therapy may be employed by those who wish to avoid surgery, and surgery can be saved for adults with chronic typical fissure when medical treatments fail.

Author's Conclusion

Non-surgical treatment of anal fissures such as nitroglycerine and lignocaine ointments are straightforward and successful, and it avoids the incontinence risk of sphincterotomy. Low recurrence rates and little adverse effects have been seen after topical ointments.

Early clinical trials using 0.2% nitroglycerin produced good results, and thus raised the possibility that it could be used to treat anal fissures. The majority of investigations have attempted to define the function of 0.2% nitroglycerin as an exogenous nitric oxide-producing agent, which is a critical neurotransmitter involved in internal anal sphincter relaxation. The efficiency of 0.2% nitroglycerin was assessed in these earlier investigations using anal manometry and squeezing pressure measurement. Manometry revealed a 2% decrease in maximal resting pressure and an 11% decrease in squeezing pressure. This is similar to the criteria applied in this study, where improvement in pain and healing of the fissure were employed to evaluate therapy efficacy in lieu of objective data..

In order to relax the sphincter, less invasive methods have been developed. Until the fissure closes, topical medication such nitroglycerin can be used to temporarily or "medical sphincterotomy" internal sphincter tensions. We certified that non-operative care of anal fissure is successful by investigating the roles of several nonsurgical methods in the treatment of chronic and acute anal fissure at Provincial hospital, Janakpur, Nepal.

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